

Exergy Analysis of Rice Straw Fired Boiler

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ABSTRACT

Exergy analysis is great tool to identify the inefficient energy utilization in a system. Effective energy utilization and its management for minimizing losses has made researchers to look for efficient energy consumption & conversion. Based on several research activity and visit to a rice straw fired power plant, some key observation has made and is presented in this paper The aim of this paper is to be find out amount and source of irreversibility's generated in boiler of 33 TPH boiler in 8 MW AFBC boiler power plant so that any process in the system that having largest energy destruction can be identified.

Keywords: *Exergy Analysis, Rice straw, AFBC Boiler, Biomass, Boiler Exergy analysis.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The general energy supply and environmental situation requires an improved utilization of energy sources. Complexity of power generating units has been increased considerably. There is increasing demand of strictly guaranteed performance, which require thermodynamic calculation of high accuracy. [1] The most commonly used method for evaluating the efficiency of an energy conversion process is the first law analysis. However, there is increasing interest in the combined utilization of the first and second laws of thermodynamics, using such concept as exergy analysis, entropy generation and irreversibility (exergy destruction) in order to evaluate the efficiency with which the available energy is consumed. [2]

Exergetic analysis is a useful tool for more efficient use of energy because it enables the locations type and true magnitude of wastes and losses to be determined. An exergy analysis usually aimed to determine the maximum performance of the system and identify the sites of exergy destruction. Exergy analysis of a complex system can be performed by analyzing the main sites of exergy destruction shows the direction for potential improvements.

In this study an exergy analysis of biomass fired boiler from India is carried out. This exergy analysis will help us to track the maximum losses in power plant in an efficient way. The biomass used as fuel is rice straw which is plenty in northern states of India once harvesting is done. Rice straw fired boilers have high maintenance due high ash contain. Also it has low calorific value so any even small percentage increase in efficiency will make a difference in economic point of view. Also rice straw after harvesting is open burned in fields which causes lot of air pollution. Promotion of rice straw as fuel in these biomass power plants could reduce the air pollution occurring every year. The power plant is 8 MW capacity situated in Abohar town from Punjab State.

1. Plant Description:

This thermal power plant is situated in Punjab state near Abohar town. Currently the plant uses mixed fuel such as rice straw, cotton straw, wheat straw, mustard straw etc. The electricity generation capacity of this plant is 8 MW. The combustion

technology used in this plant is atmospheric fluidized bed combustion (AFBC). The steam flow rate is 33 TPH with super heater outlet pressure of 66 kg/cm² and temperature of 460 °C.

Feed water is supplied to economizer through deaerator at pressure of 90 kg/cm² and temperature 102 °C. This water gets heated up to 250 °C and is supplied to steam drum. The level of steam drum is maintained around 40 %. The saturated steam is supplied to series of super heaters and its pressure and temperature is raised till 469 °C at outlet of main steam stop valve (MSSV). Shredded biomass is supplied with the help of four screw feeders (2 on each side) as shown in fig 2.1. Fuel is supplied up to feeders with the help of belt conveyors and also one return conveyor is provided to return excess shredded fuel. All of the screw feeders are controlled automatically with respect to load on turbine. As the load decreases so the required steam flow rate also need to be decreased, this is achieved by reducing fuel feed rate i.e by controlling screw feeders. The feed water used in boiler is treated in a water treatment plant. The hardness of the water is checked and controlled to avoid deposition due to scaling. Raw water coming from different sources contains dissolved salts and undissolved or suspended impurities. This salts and suspended particles will from scale inside the heat exchanger tubes eventually and thus they will create excessive pressure and thermal stress inside the heat exchanger, which may lead to explosion and serious hazards for boilers. Also the salts can corrode various parts of boilers such as tubes and turbine blades. There is demineralization and reverse osmosis to remove this salts. This water after treating is supplied to deaerator where it is heated by mixing with low pressure steam to remove dissolved oxygen. Deaerator is a contact type open heater in which dissolved oxygen in the feed water is removed by mechanical means.

The feed water from deaerator which is at 102 °C is pumped to economizer up to 90 kg/cm². The air is supplied at pressure of 730 mm of WC at under the bed material which is sand. After combustion in bed of boiler the flue gas temperature at exit of furnace is reached up to 720 °C. This flue gas first passes through series of super heaters to super heat the water up to 420 °C. Then it passes through economizer to heat the water up to 213 °C from

102 °C. And finally it passes through air preheater to heat the air. The layout of power plant with air, flue gas path and water/steam flow path is shown in the picture below (Fig. 2.1) taken from power plant operating room. This flue gas which mainly contains fly ash particles is treated in electro precipitator (ESP) and then left out to environment through chimney.

2. Exergy Analysis of Boiler:

3.1. Exergy Analysis of

$$\begin{aligned} \text{GCV of fuel} &= 2984 \text{ kcal/kg} \\ &= 12473.12 \text{ KJ/kg} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Ratio of chemical exergy to HHV} = 1.05 \quad [5]$$

$$\text{Exergy of fuel} = 13096.776 \quad \text{KJ/kg}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Fuel Feed rate} &= 240 \text{ ton/day} \\ &= 2.77 \text{ kg/s} \end{aligned}$$

$$X_f = 36379.93 \text{ kW}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Theoretical air} &= 11.521 \%C + 34.56 \%H + 4.32(\%S-\%O) \\ \text{(using table 3.1)} & \\ &= 4.53 \text{ kg/kg of fuel} \end{aligned}$$

3.2. Exergy of feed water

$$\text{Formula: } X_w = (C_{pw}) (T_w - T_o) - T_o \ln (T_w/T_o) \quad [3]$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_w: & \text{ temp of inlet feed water after dearator} & T_o: & \text{ ambient temp} \\ & 102 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} & & \\ 27 & \text{ }^\circ\text{C} & & \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & 375 \text{ K} \\ & 300 \text{ K} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Water feed rate} &= 33.5 \text{ tph} & \text{Specific heat of water} &= 4.187 \text{ kJ/kg} \\ & & & \\ & & & = 9.30 \text{ kg/s} \end{aligned}$$

$$X_w = 2299.234669 \text{ kW}$$

3.3. Exergy change in economizer

$$\text{Formula: } X_e = C_{pw}(T_{eo} - T_{ei}) - T_o (\ln (T_{eo}/T_{ei})) \quad [3]$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_{ei} &= \text{Inlet water temp to economizer} & T_{eo} &= \text{Outlet water} \\ & \text{temp from economizer (using table 3.2)} & & \\ & = 102 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} = 375 \text{ K} & & = 213 \end{aligned}$$

$$^\circ\text{C} = 486 \text{ K}$$

$$X_e = 3600.991497 \text{ kW}$$

3.4. Exergy of supplied air

$$\text{Formula: } X_a = C_{pa} (T_a - T_o) - T_o (\ln (T_a/T_o)) \quad [3]$$

$$\begin{aligned} T_a &= \text{furnace air inlet temp after APH} = 132 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} & T_o &= 300 \text{ K} \\ & \text{(using table 3.2)} & & \\ & & & = 405 \text{ K} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Theoretical air} &= 4.53 \text{ kg/kg of fuel} \\ C_{pa} &= 1.005 \text{ kJ/kgK} \\ m_a &= 17.607 \text{ kg/s} \quad (40 \% \text{ excess air}) \end{aligned}$$

$$272.79 \text{ kW}$$

3.5. Exergy Change in Drum

$$\text{Formula: } X_d = (h_{do} - h_{di}) - T_o (s_{do} - s_{di}) \quad [3]$$

Properties of steam at inlet of drum

$$\begin{aligned} T_{di} &= 213 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} & p_{di} &= 88 \text{ kg/cm}^2 \quad (\text{assume } 2 \text{ kg/cm}^2 \\ & & & \text{pressure drop in economiser)} \\ h_{di} &= 913.63 \text{ kJ/kg} & s_{di} &= 2.442 \text{ kJ/kgK} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Steam flow rate} = 34.6 \text{ tph}$$

$$= 9.61 \text{ kg/s}$$

Properties of steam at outlet of drum

(using table 3.2)

$$p_{do} (\text{sat}) = 80 \text{ kg/cm}^2$$

$$h_{do} = 2761.5 \text{ kJ/kg} \quad s_{do} = 5.7568 \text{ kJ/kgK}$$

$$X_d = 8202.410556 \text{ kW}$$

3.6. Exergy Change in Super heater

$$\text{Formula } X_s = (h_{so} - h_{si}) - T_{si} (s_{so} - s_{si}) \quad [3]$$

Properties of steam at inlet of superheater

$$\begin{aligned} T_{si} &= \text{Superheater inlet temp} & p &= 80 \text{ kg/cm}^2 \\ & = 293.79 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} = 566.79 \text{ K} \end{aligned}$$

$$h_{si} = 2761.5 \text{ kJ/kg} \quad s_{si} = 5.7568 \text{ kJ/kgK}$$

Properties of steam at outlet of superheater

$$T_{so} = 460 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad p = 66.7 \text{ kg/cm}^2$$

$$h_{so} = 3318.9 \text{ kJ/kg} \quad s_{so} = 6.7009 \text{ kJ/kgK}$$

$$X_{sh} = 2635.078333 \text{ kW}$$

3.7. Exergy change in Air Preheater:

$$X_{aph} = C_{pa} (T_{ao} - T_{ai}) - T_{ai} (\ln (T_{ao}/T_{ai})) \quad [3]$$

$$m_a = 17.61 \text{ kg/s}$$

$$T_{ai} = 27 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} \quad C_{pa} = 1.005 \text{ kJ/kgK}$$

$$= 300$$

T_{ao} = air temperature at outlet of APH

$$= 132 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$$

$$= 405 \text{ K}$$

$$X_{aph} = 272.7926532 \text{ k}$$

3.8. Exergy in flue gases leaving APH

$$\text{Formula } X_{fi} = C_{pg} (T_{fo} - T_o) - T_o (\ln (T_{fo}/T_o)) \quad [3]$$

C_{pg} = specific heat of flue gases = 1.2 kJ/kgK

$$\begin{aligned} T_{fo} &= \text{Temperature of flue gas leaving APH (using table 3.2)} \\ & = 163 \text{ }^\circ\text{C} = 436 \text{ K} \end{aligned}$$

$$T_o = 300 \text{ K}$$

$$\text{Energy Balance in APH: } m_g \times C_{pg} (T_{fi} - T_{fo}) = m_a \times C_{pa} (T_{ao} - T_{ai})$$

$$\begin{aligned} m_g &= \text{mass flow rate of flue gases from APH} \\ & = 22.118 \text{ kg/s} \end{aligned}$$

	10. ID inlet temp	Deg. C	147
	11. APH outlet temp	Deg. C	132
E	Air pressure and drafts		
	1. Chamber no. 1 pressure	mm WC	730
	2. Chamber no. 2 pressure	mm WC	730
	3. Chamber no. 3 pressure	mm WC	730
	4. Furnace pressure	mm WC	1.7
	5. Economizer inlet pressure	mm WC	-30
	6. APH inlet pressure	mm WC	-65
	7. ESP inlet pressure	mm WC	-125
F	Flow		
	1. Water flow	tph	33.5
	2. Steam flow	tph	34.6
	3. Generation	kWhr	7958

Table 4.1 Exergy Utilization and Percentage Distribution

Exergy Utilized in	Value (kW)	Percentage
Fuel (supplied)	36379.93	100%
APH	272.7927	1%
Economiser	3600.991	10%
Drum	8202.411	23%
Superheater	12627.84	35%
Not recovered	11675.89	32%

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REFERENCES

1. Cengel Y. A, M.A. Boles, Thermodynamics: An Engineering Approach, Tata McGraw hill Publication, 2004.
2. Cengel Y.A, Wood B, Dincer, Is bigger Thermodynamically better. Exergy An International J.,2002:2:62-68
3. Sarang J Gulhane, Prof.Amit Kumar Thakur, "Exergy Analysis of Boiler In cogeneration Thermal Power Plant", Volume-02, Issue-10, 2013, American Journal of Engineering Research
4. Krishan Kumar, Dharmendra Patel, Vinod Sehriu, avat, Tarun Gupta, "Performance and Exergy Analysis of the Boiler", 2319-706, 2013, International Journal of Science and Research.
5. Guohui Song, Laihong Shen, and Jun Xiao, "Estimating Specific Chemical Exergy of Biomass from Basic Analysis Data", 50 (16), pp 9758–9766, 2011, Industrial and Engineering Chemistry Research, Americanf Chemical Society.

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